

Chromatographic Separations on Anion-Exchange Papers

R. K. GHATUARY

Deptt. of Chemistry, Suri Vidyasagar College, Suri, (W.B.)

and

ASIT KUMAR SEN*

Deptt. of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan

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A comparative study of the chromatographic behaviour of anions phosphate, vanadate, chromate, molybdate and tungstate on anion-exchange papers and Whatman no. 1. filter papers using identical aqueous-organic mixed solvent system has been made. The selectivity of separation increases greatly in the case of anion exchange papers in which the separation is sharp and the spots are distinct in contrast to Whatman no. 1. filter papers where wide and diffused bands are obtained. Methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, n-butyl alcohol, iso-amyl alcohol in combination with acetone, hydrochloric acid or acetic acid of different molarity have been used as the developing solvent. The anions phosphate, vanadate, chromate, molybdate, tungstate are separated from each other when they are present in a binary or in a complex mixture. The method is applied to analyse an alloy steel.

THE importance of inorganic ion-exchangers for the separation of metal ions has been increased during the last ten years. Among different inorganic ion exchangers, hydrated stannic oxide acts as an anion exchanger at $pH < 6.0^1$ and as a cation-exchanger at $pH > 6.0^{1-3}$.

Combined ion-exchange and solvent extraction (C.I.E.S.E.) technique has been utilised by several authors as a useful tool for the separation of different metal ions in mixture using usual synthetic organic ion exchange papers⁴⁻¹². A few works with C.I.E.S.E. technique have been reported so far using inorganic ion exchangers¹³ and systematic studies on the development of C.I.E.S.E. technique for the separation of anions are still lacking.

In this paper are reported the results of systematic studies using inorganic anion exchanger, hydrated stannic oxide, impregnated papers and mixed aqueous organic solvent system. The anions phosphate, vanadate, chromate, molybdate, tungstate are separated from each other when they are present in a binary or in a complex mixture. The aqueous organic solvent system studied are: The ternary mixtures of methanol, ethanol, n-butanol or isoamyl alcohol as one of the components and acetone and hydrochloric acid or 20% acetic acid as the other two components. A comparative study has also been made with ordinary Whatman No. 1. filter papers using identical solvent compositions.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents

Developments were carried out in (30×7cm) glass jars using the ascending method on (25×3 cm) paper strips. Sodium stannate was of reagent grade quality (U.S.S.R.). All other chemicals and solvents used were either of B.D.H. or E. Merck analar grade. The anion solution used for separation contained one mg. of each salt per ml. of the solution. Sodium or potassium or ammonium salts were used.

Preparation of hydrated stannic oxide papers

Each paper strip was dipped in freshly prepared 1(M) aqueous solution of sodium stannate for 10 seconds. It was then removed and kept horizontally at (30±5)° in air oven for 30 minutes. Dried papers were then dipped in 1 (M) aqueous solution of ammonium sulphate for 10 seconds and dried horizontally at first at (30±5)° for two hours and then at (85±5)° for one hour. The dried papers were washed several times with double distilled water and dried at room temperature.

In order to check the conversion of sodium stannate into hydrated stannic oxide via ammonium stannate, 25 ml. of 1(M) sodium stannate solution was taken and tin was estimated iodimetrically¹⁴. Again, 25 ml of 1(M) sodium stannate solution was taken and was mixed with 25 ml. of 1(M) ammonium sulphate solution.

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The white precipitate of hydrated tin dioxide was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at 85° for one hour and weighed to constant weight.

TABLE NO. 1—CONVERSION OF SODIUM STANNATE INTO HYDRATED SnO_2

No. of obs.	Volume of 1(M) $\text{Na}_2\text{SnO}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution taken each time (ml.)	Amount of SnO_2 obtained iodimetrically (g)	Amount of SnO_2 obtained at 85°C. (g)	Amount of SnO_2 obtained at 800°C (g)
1.	25	3.545	3.951	3.521
2.	25	3.543	3.952	3.523
3.	25	3.544	3.956	3.525

It is evident from the above data (Table-1) that the conversion of sodium stannate into tin dioxide via ammonium stannate under the condition is almost quantitative.

In order to determine the composition of the impregnated paper, ten numbers of each of the plain Whatman No. 1. papers and hydrated stannic oxide impregnated papers were ignited at 850° and weighed to constant weight. The average amount of SnO_2 obtained per sheet of Whatman papers is 315.70 mg. and the amount of SnO_2 per square centimetre is 4.20 mg.

It was experimentally observed that hydrated stannic oxide prepared from sodium stannate by precipitation and dried at $(80 \pm 5^\circ)$ for one hour as above was chemically stable in the solvent systems used in the chromatographic separation.

Spraying Reagents

Usual spraying reagents were used for the detection of different ions.

General procedure

Paper strips were lightly marked with pencil line to indicate the starting and finishing position of the solvent fronts and the starting position of the ions to be separated. The mixture of anions was then spotted on the pencil line and allowed to come in contact with solvent mixture in each case by ascending paper chromatography. Care had been taken to keep the diameter of the spot within 5 mm. The development of the spots were then carried out with the spraying reagent. The R_T and R_L values were then measured atleast for triplicate runs and their average were noted. A series of chromatographic runs were also made using the identical solvent system on hydrated stannic oxide loaded papers and ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers.

Results and Discussion

The R_T and R_L values for the anions in different solvent systems are given in Tables 2 to 6.

TABLE NO. 2— R_T , R_L AND R_F VALUES OF PHOSPHATE AND MOLYBDATE ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE PAPER AND WHATMAN-1 PAPER AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$.

Solvent system	Time—One hour	
	(R_T-R_L) R_F value on hydrated stannic oxide paper	(R_T-R_L) R_F value on Whatman-1 paper
HCl(6M)-acetone - CH_3OH = 3:1:1 (vol/vol.)	molybdate (0.58-0.75)0.66 phosphate (0.15-0.32)0.23	phosphate (0.89-1.00)0.94 molybdate (0.63-0.86)0.74
HCl(6M)-acetone - $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ = 3:1:1 (vol/vol)	molybdate (0.58-0.67)0.62 phosphate (0.05-0.14)0.05	phosphate (0.84-1.00)0.92 molybdate (0.60-0.7)0.65
HCl(6M)-acetone -n-butanol = 3:1:1 (vol/vol)	molybdate (0.48-0.66)0.57 phosphate (0.00-0.00)0.00	phosphate (0.86-1.00)0.93 molybdate (0.69-0.77)0.73
HCl(6M)-acetone -isoamylalcohol = 3:1:1 (vol/vol)	molybdate (0.64-0.80)0.72 phosphate (0.20-0.34)0.27	phosphate (0.84-1.00)0.92 molybdate (0.50-0.72)0.61

TABLE NO. 3— R_T AND R_L VALUES OF CHROMATE AND PHOSPHATE, CHROMATE AND VANADATE, CHROMATE AND MOLYBDATE ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE PAPER AND WHATMAN-1 PAPER AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$.

Solvent system	Time—One hour	
	(R_T - R_L) value on hydrated stannic oxide paper	(R_T - R_L) value on Whatman-1 paper
HCl(2M)-acetone-n-butanol=3:1:1 (vol/vol).	(a) Chromate (0.72-0.80) Phosphate (0.00-0.00)	Chromate (0.77-0.96) Phosphate (0.77-0.96)
	(b) Chromate (0.72-0.78) Vanadate (0.24-0.31)	Chromate (0.77-0.96) Vanadate (0.77-0.96)
	(c) Chromate (0.73-0.78) Molybdate (0.00-0.04)	Chromate (0.70-0.96) molybdate (0.70-0.96)

TABLE NO. 4—SELECTIVE SEPARATION OF TUNGSTATE FROM THE SYNTHETIC MIXTURE OF TUNGSTATE, PHOSPHATE, MOLYBDATE AND VANADATE.

Solvent system	Temperature= $(30 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$	Time—One hour.
	(R_T - R_L) value on hydrated stannic oxide paper	(R_T - R_L) value on Whatman-1 paper
20% CH_3COOH -acetone- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ =2:1:2 (vol/vol)	tungstate (0.82-0.92) phosphate (0.00-0.00) molybdate (0.00-0.00) vanadate (0.00-0.00)	*tungstate (0.82-0.94) *phosphate (0.72-0.84) molybdate (0.29-0.45) vanadate (0.12-0.20)

* Note :—With Whatman—1 paper overlapping of tungstate and phosphate took place.

TABLE NO. 5— R_T AND R_L VALUES OF TUNGSTATE, CHROMATE AND VANADATE ; TUNGSTATE, CHROMATE AND PHOSPHATE ; TUNGSTATE, CHROMATE AND MOLYBDATE ON HYDRATED STANNIC OXIDE PAPER AND WHATMAN-1 PAPER AT $(30 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$.

Solvent system	Time—One hour	
	(R_T - R_L) value on hydrated stannic oxide paper	(R_T - R_L) value on Whatman-1 paper
20% CH_3COOH -acetone- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ =2.5 :1:1.5 (vol/vol)	(a) tungstate (0.88-0.98) chromate (0.25-0.37) vanadate (0.00-0.00)	*tungstate (0.87-0.94) *chromate (0.69-0.89) vanadate (0.05-0.22)
	(b) tungstate (0.90-0.98) chromate (0.25-0.39) phosphate (0.00-0.00)	*tungstate (0.87-0.94) *chromate (0.69-0.89) *phosphate (0.66-0.70)
	(c) tungstate (0.88-0.98) chromate (0.26-0.37) molybdate (0.00-0.00)	*tungstate (0.87-0.94) *chromate (0.69-0.89) molybdate (0.16-0.46)

* Note :—With Whatman No. 1 paper, in all the cases overlapping of tungstate and chromate, in some cases overlapping of chromate and phosphate took place.

TABLE NO. 6—SEPARATION OF CHROMATE, MOLYBDATE, VANADATE AND PHOSPHATE FROM EACH OTHER IN A MIXTURE.

Solvent system	Temperature= $(30 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$	Time—One hour
	(R_T - R_L) value on hydrated stannic oxide paper	(R_T - R_L) value on Whatman-1 paper
HCl(2M)-acetone- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ =3:1:1 (vol/vol)	Chromate (0.67-0.75) molybdate (0.20-0.27) vanadate (0.05-0.11) phosphate (0.00-0.00)	*Chromate (0.87-0.98) *molybdate (0.65-0.78) *vanadate (0.80-0.91) *phosphate (0.78-0.90)

* Note :— With Whatman-1 paper overlapping of all four ions took place.

In the case of binary mixture of phosphate and molybdate (Table-2) poor separation and in some cases no separation at all were observed with ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers, whereas the separation was sharp and spots were distinct in hydrated stannic oxide loaded papers, using same time and exactly identical conditions. With Whatman No. 1 papers diffused and wide spots were observed. Another remarkable observation was that in the case of ordinary paper phosphate occupied higher position than molybdate, but with hydrated stannic oxide loaded paper the case was reversed. That was either due to strong adsorption of phosphate on hydrated stannic oxide or due to the formation of insoluble stannic phosphate. In the presence of 6(M) hydrochloric acid and small amount of molybdate the probability of the formation of phosphomolybdic acid was negligible. Molybdenum moved on the paper most probably as the species MoO_2Cl_2 . At 6(M) hydrochloric acid the species was weakly absorbed by anion exchanger. When the acidity of hydrochloric acid decreased to 2(M) molybdate did not move and was adsorbed strongly by the exchanger (Table-3).

It was also observed that the difference of R_F values of the anions calculated from R_T and R_L values (Table-2) increased with the increase of molecular weight of the primary alcohols. The difference of R_F values increased in the order $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} < \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} < n\text{-butyl alcohol}$, but the difference of R_F values for isoamyl alcohol were intermediate between that of CH_3OH and $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$.

It was also observed that with hydrated stannic oxide loaded paper the R_F values for phosphate and molybdate were maximum for isoamyl alcohol but with primary alcohols the R_F values for both decreased with the increase of molecular weight. This order of decreasing R_F values with increasing molecular weight of the primary alcohols was not so regular with ordinary Whatman No. 1 papers.

In the case of tungstate and vanadate, tungstate and phosphate, tungstate and molybdate it was found that almost in all Whatman no. 1 papers tungstate was widely distributed throughout the paper and no distinct and clear cut spot was observed. In many cases there were overlapping of the two and separations were not possible. But with hydrated stannic oxide loaded papers the tungstate was well separated from others and sharp well defined spots were obtained. From the R_T and R_L values of tungstate, phosphate, molybdate and vanadate it was quite clear that tungstate could be selectively separated from the mixture of phosphate, vanadate and molybdate. This selective separation of tungstate was obtained from the synthetic mixture of phosphate, vanadate, molybdate and tungstate (Table-4).

In the case of chromate and vanadate, chromate and phosphate, chromate and molybdate (Table-3) overlapping took place with Whatman No. 1 papers and no separation was possible, whereas with hydrated stannic oxide loaded papers chromate was separated from phosphate, vanadate and molybdate from its binary mixture. From the study of the R_T and R_L

values of chromate, vanadate, phosphate and molybdate it was found that with hydrated stannic oxide loaded paper chromate could be selectively separated from the mixture of vanadate, phosphate and molybdate. A synthetic mixture of phosphate, chromate, vanadate and molybdate was used and a clear cut separation was obtained. [Table No, 6, Fig. 1, b]. The difference of R_T and R_L values of different ions indicated that ethyl alcohol-acetone-hydrochloric acid 2(M) and n-butanol-acetone-hydrochloric acid 2(M) were the best medium. Since n-butanol is immiscible with 2(M) hydrochloric acid, it is difficult to study the separation at different proportions of the solvent mixture. This difficulty did not arise with ethyl alcohol-acetone-hydrochloric acid 2(M) system. This developing solvent mixture was, therefore, the best solvent for all such separations.

In the case of ternary separation of tungstate, chromate and vanadate, tungstate, chromate and phosphate and tungstate, chromate and molybdate (Table-5) it was observed that no separation was possible with Whatman No. 1 paper, but clear cut separation was achieved with hydrated stannic oxide loaded papers.

Application to an alloy steel (BAS no. 64A)

200 mg. of the steel was taken and solution was made by usual procedure¹⁴. Total volume of the solution was made 100 ml. so that 1 ml. of the solution contained 2 mg. of the alloy steel. The solution was tested for chromate, tungstate, vanadate and molybdate, and positive results were obtained¹⁵. As in the previous cases the alloy solution was spotted on the papers and allowed to come in contact with the developing solution of 20% acetic acid-acetone-ethyl alcohol (2:1:2 vol/vol) for one hour. After drying the papers were first sprayed with (1:1) hydrochloric acid and then warmed. Tungstate and vanadate produced yellow colour. Then chromate was detected by diphenyl carbazide and molybdate by hydrogen sulphide. Good separation was observed [Table-7,]. It was noted that due to presence of mineral acid in the alloy steel solution vanadate was eluted and moved a little upward on hydrated stannic oxide papers.

Fig. 1. Separation of the anions on : (a) Whatman no 1 filter paper (b) Hydrated stannic oxide loaded paper

TABLE NO. 7—ANALYSIS OF AN ALLOY STEEL (BAS NO. 64a)

Temperature=(35±1)°C		Time—One hour
Solvent system	(R_T-R_L) value on hydrated stannic oxide paper	(R_T-R_L) value on Whatman-1 paper
20% CH ₃ COOH-acetone-C ₂ H ₅ OH =2:1:2 (vol/vol)	tungstate (0.85-0.96) chromate (0.47-0.57) vanadate (0.13-0.20) molybdate (0.00-0.00)	*tungstate (0.82-0.98) *chromate (0.75-0.98) vanadate (0.09-0.18) molybdate (0.30-0.40)

*Note :—With Whatman-1 paper overlapping of tungstate and chromate took place.

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